

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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MEDICATION ADHERENCE IN HISPANIC
RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS PATIENTS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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May 2017

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ABSTRACT

Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) is an autoimmune inflammatory joint disease of unknown etiology that affects not only joints but also other organ systems in the body. Rheumatoid arthritis is a chronic and incurable condition. However, symptoms can be effectively and durably controlled with medications. Uncontrolled RA can lead to irreversible joint damage, significant functional disability, poor quality of life, enhanced comorbidities, and significant morbidity and mortality. When patients adhere to treatment regimens, disability can be prevented. When RA patients are treated early, they maintain their functional ability (Heimans et al., 2015). As Radner, Smolen, & Aletaha (2014) point out, achieving clinical remission is the goal to prevent joint destruction and possible disability. The patient's decision to take medication is typically based on knowledge and beliefs about their illness and treatment regimen (van den Bemt, Zwikker, & van den Ende, 2012).

The problem that this project addressed was to identify barriers to medication adherence among Hispanic with RA in order to develop an education pamphlet designed to increase medication adherence. The aim of this project was to address the gaps in the existing literature by combining information about education and non-adherence by increasing the knowledge about the disease progression of RA among Hispanics to increase RA medication adherence. Poor treatment adherence was a major contributor to disease progression, which can lead to disability. Among the Hispanic population, the

adherence rates were 49% (White, 2014). Patient's knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes contribute to adherence. The present project found that 64 percent of the study participants were non-adherent to their RA medications. Thus, participants with low medication concerns and high necessity were non-adherent. It appeared that adherence to medication had multiple influences, with education being a contributor. Individuals with higher education were more likely to adhere to their medication regimen. The PKQ results showed that the majority of the participants had low knowledge regarding their RA. This data is used as baseline information in the development and in the implementation of the the educational pamphlet. The self-administered post-questionnaire will be distributed after implementation of the education pamphlet to determine if there was a change in knowledge, beliefs, and medication adherence.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
LIST OF TABLES.....	vii
LIST OF FIGURES	viii
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	ix
INTRODUCTION	1
Background.....	2
Medication and Imaging for RA Control.....	3
RA Disability and Impact	4
Health Care Cost Associated with Non-adherence.....	5
Factors Related to Non-adherence	5
Problem Statement.....	6
Purpose Statement.....	6
Supporting Framework	7
Health Belief Model.....	7
Health Belief Model Constructs	9
Health Belief Model Literature Review.....	10
Application of HBM in Medication among Hispanic RA Patients	11
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	14
Facilitators and Barriers to Treatment Adherence.....	14
Facilitators to Medication Adherence.....	15
Self-Efficacy	15
Barriers to Medication Adherence.....	16
Patient Education to Medication Adherence	18
Hispanic Patients and Medication Adherence	19
Interventions to Improve Adherence	20
METHODS	22
Study Design.....	22
Protection of Human Subjects	22
Settings.....	23

Sample	23
Procedures.....	23
Instruments.....	25
Project Question.....	27
Operational Definitions.....	27
Assumptions.....	28
Variables	28
Data Analysis.....	29
Summary	29
RESULTS (PRE-TEST ONLY)	31
DISCUSSION	40
Future Steps	42
Conclusion	43
REFERENCES	44
APPENDIX A: IRB APPROVAL LETTER.....	57
APPENDIX B: APPROVED SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRES.....	59
APPENDIX C: TABLE OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL	75

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Demographic Data of the Study Participants.....	32

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Extended health belief model	7
2. Modified HBM for Hispanic RA patients	12
3. Correlation graph between BMQ concerns, necessity and SMAQ adherence	34
4. Interaction effect graph between BMQ necessity and concern	36
5. Histogram distribution of the PKQ total results	37
6. Histogram of PKQ total scores results of RA patients	38
7. Correlation coefficient line graph of CDAI scores and age.....	39
8. Correlation coefficient line graph of DAS28 CRP scores and age.....	40

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

First and foremost, I would like to thank God for giving me this opportunity and the talent to pursue my last educational endeavor. Thank you Dr. Ayman Tailakh and Dr. Jean O'Neil for guiding me throughout my DNP program. Without your support and enthusiasm, I wouldn't have been able to finish my project and graduate. I also would like to thank Dr. George A. Karpouzas for encouraging and supporting my project implementation in our clinic. Special thanks to Elizabeth Echevarria-Hernandez for helping me implement and distribute my protocols throughout the clinic. Without you, I would not have been able to gather my data. Thanks also to Dr. Sarah R. Ormseth for all your help in conducting my data analysis. To Sarah Douville for all the beyond belief help and support you've given me these past two years. You are the best! And to Dr. Gina Armendariz, there would be no graduation for me without your help and guidance from beginning to end. We spent many hours editing my papers side by side. I also would like to thank my friends; Divine Mercy Prayer Group, the priests at Nativity Catholic Church, the nuns at Puso Ng Carmelo and all my friends of faith who prayed for me to pass all my classes and graduate. Another special thanks to the patients who participated in my project. I thank you all, from the bottom of my heart. I would like to send out a special thanks to Judge Tomson T. Ong, who was my motivator in applying to the DNP program. You gave me faith in myself to pursue my dream! Finally, thank you to Cohort 4, specifically, Nancy Jo, Rachel, and Jutara. You guys made this program bearable and fun! I needed you guys throughout the program and you were there for me!

Last but not least, this project is dedicated to my family; my parents, brother, and my son, Nico. You are my life and driving force in all that I do! Thank you for your unconditional love and unending support you have always given to me. I would not have been able to finish this journey without all of you. You all are truly “THE WIND BENEATH MY WINGS.” I love you!

INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) is an autoimmune inflammatory joint disease of unknown etiology that affects not only joints but also other organ systems in the body. This disease manifests as joint swelling, tenderness or pain, as well as morning stiffness of the small joints of the hands and feet, lasting more than one hour (Skirvin et al., 2014). If the symptoms are present for less than six months, the condition is identified as early RA, whereas symptom duration over six months qualifies as established RA (Skirvin et al., 2014). Rheumatoid arthritis is a chronic, incurable condition. However, symptoms can be effectively and durably controlled with medications. Despite well-accepted, published guidelines for effective disease control and a plethora of available treatments, many patients are non-adherent to their medication regimens (Elliot, 2008; Salt & Frazier, 2011). Uncontrolled RA can lead to irreversible joint damage, significant functional disability, poor quality of life, enhanced comorbidities, and significant morbidity and mortality.

There are 1.3 million adults in the United States afflicted with RA (Curtis et al., 2015). The cost of treating RA in the United States was \$128 billion in 2003, with \$47 billion attributed to indirect costs and \$80.8 billion in direct costs (CDC 2015; Skirvin et al., 2014). Although not reported in the most recent update from the CDC, current cost will be significantly higher given the increased costs in medical care. Direct costs of RA treatment include medications, doctor visits, drug complications, and disease progression (Skirvin et al., 2014). Indirect costs include loss of earning due to disability and absenteeism (CDC 2015). The total cost of RA is high with an estimate of 100 and 300 billion dollars annually (Iuga & McGuire, 2014; Zwikker, van Dulmen, den Broeder, van

den Bemt, & van den Ende, 2014). These costs are increased when patients are non-adherent to their medications.

Medication adherence is a mutual agreement between the patient and healthcare provider. With such an agreement, the patient commits to take medications as prescribed by a healthcare provider (van den Bemt et al., 2012). This agreement becomes important and directly affects treatment goals and outcomes. This project will discuss the role of medication adherence in Hispanic RA patient's ability to control disease progression, prevent disability, improve quality of life, and decrease health care costs.

Background

Patients with RA assume that having bearable joint pain, occasional joint swelling, and morning stiffness are normal and part of the disease process. The main goal of treatment in RA is improving quality of life by symptom control, prevention of joint damage, and being able to function and participate fully in both social and job-related activities. The most important and efficient way to achieve these goals is by controlling or eliminating inflammation (Smolen et al., 2016). This is generally defined as disease remission, requiring absence of swollen or tender joints.

The percentage of RA patients who are non-adherent can be from as low as 30% to as high as 80% (van den Bemt & van Lankveld, 2007; van den Bemt et al., 2009; van den Bemt et al., 2012). Thus, poor medication adherence is a significant issue affecting quality of life among RA patients. Improving medication adherence should lead to an increase in the effectiveness of treatment and a corresponding reduction in healthcare costs (Joplin, van der Zwan, & Wong, 2015). Rheumatoid Arthritis is an incurable disease but controllable. Early disease management can lead to a reduction in joint

damage, maintenance of physical function, and better quality of life (Heiman et al., 2015). There are available medications that when taken appropriately and continuously, will help to put RA into remission.

Medications and Imaging for RA Control

There are a variety of conventional, synthetic disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs) used to treat RA. These drugs include Methotrexate, Leflunomide, Sulfasalazine, Plaquenil, and Minocycline. Additionally, there are biologic therapies that have been proven effective in the treatment of RA such as anti-tumor necrosis factor (TNF) (Adalimumab, Certolizumab, Etanercept, Golimumab, and Infliximab), Janus Kinase (JAK) inhibitor (Tofacitinib), Anti-CD20 Monoclonal Antibody (Rituximab), Interleukin (IL)-6 Receptor Inhibitor (Tocilizumab), and T-cell Costimulatory Blocker (Abatacept) (Skirvin et al., 2014). Individuals with high disease activity who stop their treatment or switch their biologic, experience increased progression of the disease as seen through radiographic imaging compared to those who continue their treatment without changes (Ornberg et al., 2014). Patients often do not realize their disease is progressing because of lack of immediate symptoms. Therefore, they may stop taking their medications, which then creates a barrier to medication adherence. Disease progression is only evidenced by radiographic imaging of joints, not the patient's symptomology. Radiographic progression is structural damage represented in worsening bone and cartilage destruction as a result of ongoing, and uncontrolled inflammation.

Physicians evaluate the damage periodically with the use of radiographic imaging, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), or Ultrasound (US) of the hands and feet (Ornberg et al., 2014). Prevention of structural damage is a major goal in the treatment of RA

(Smolen et al., 2016). Patients are often misled by the fact that they are not experiencing pain. Thus, they become non-adherent to their medication regimen. Nevertheless, subclinical joint swelling, erosion, and narrowing continue. The patient does not associate the clinical symptoms and signs of disease progression as evidence of joint damage (Ciubotariu et al., 2014). Because the patient is not experiencing joint pain, he/she does not realize that joint damage continues to occur.

RA Disability and Impact

Control of clinical symptoms of RA is a goal of practitioners. Inadequate RA control is associated with poor quality of life. Higher disease activity is associated with greater rates of depression (Withers, Moran, Nicassio, Weisman, & Karpouzas, 2015). About 38.8 percent of RA patients have depression (Lin et al., 2015; Matcham, Rayner, Steer, & Hotopf, 2013). One-third of RA patients stop working within five years of diagnosis due to disease-associated disability. Patients who are diagnosed with RA are also more likely to receive government-funded insurance earlier than patients without RA (Birnbaum et al., 2010). This places an increasing burden on government funding to support the ongoing progression of RA.

Higher patient disability leads to increasing dependence on family or friends. The healthcare system shoulders the burden with families in providing publically funded health insurance such as Medicaid (Birnbaum et al., 2010; Kumar et al., 2013). If the RA patient is the primary provider for the family, their functional disability further strains the family unit. When patients adhere to treatment regimens, disability can be prevented. When RA patients are treated early, they maintain their functional ability (Heimans et al.,

2015). As Radner, Smolen, & Aletaha (2014) point out, achieving clinical remission is the goal to prevent joint destruction and possible disability.

HealthCare Costs Associated with Non-adherence

There are 1.3 million adults with RA in the United States incurring an “annual healthcare costs of \$8.4 billion and a total annual societal cost of \$19.3 billion” (Curtis et al., 2015), p. 318). Approximately 80% to 90% of healthcare costs come from the use of biologic medications as treatment for RA. Most biologics prevent joint damage. However, the cost for these biologics ranges from \$1,894 to \$3,598 per month, per patient (Johnston, McMorrow, Farr, Juneau, & Ogale, 2015).

Factors Related to Non-adherence

A study by Joplin et al. (2015) found a number of factors contributing to non-adherence. Low educational level and limited health literacy were identified as the two major contributing factors for predicting medication non-adherence. Limited health literacy occurs when a patient does not understand the disease process nor the usefulness of taking these expensive medications to treat RA. Other barriers to adherence include pain level, medication side effects, beliefs about medication and disease, medication knowledge, medication regimen or schedule, poor communication between patients, family members and providers, and connection to providers (Pasma, Hazes, Luime, Busschbach, & Spijker, 2014). These behaviors are relevant to RA patients and should be considered when developing a medication adherence program.

There are two types of behaviors present when a patient is non-adherent, unintentionally non-adherent and intentionally non-adherent (van de Bemt et al., 2012). The unintentional non-adherent behaviors occur when a patient is not able to take their

medication because of personal or physical inability (van de Bemt et al., 2012). Intentional non-adherent behaviors occur when a patient consciously decides not to take their medication. The patient's decision to take medication is typically based on knowledge and beliefs about their illness and treatment regimen (van de Bemt et al., 2012).

Problem Statement

The population of Hispanics in the United States was 16% in 2010 and is expected to increase to 24% by 2050 (Karpouzas et al., 2012). There are 4 million Hispanic adults with RA, and their adherence rate is as high as 49% (CDC, 2016; White, 2014). Hispanics with RA have been identified as “vulnerable patients,” their vulnerability stems from the tendency for this population to come from migrant or other low-income families with no insurance (Karpouzas et al., 2012; Withers et al., 2015). Vulnerable patients tend to have a higher self-reported disability, poorer functional outcomes, and depression (Karpouzas et al., 2012). Hispanics are at risk due to the preexisting factors, which can contribute to medication non-adherence. The problem that this project addressed was identification of barriers to medication adherence among Hispanic RA patients to develop an education pamphlet designed to increase medication adherence.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was the development and evaluation of the effectiveness of a theoretically driven educational pamphlet designed to increase medication adherence using strategies targeting Hispanic RA patients. This project addressed the gaps in the existing literature by combining information about education

and non-adherence to increase knowledge about the disease progression of RA among Hispanics in order to increase RA medication adherence, prevent further joint damage, and improve quality of life.

Supporting Framework

It is essential to use a theoretical framework to address a problem that includes patients' behaviors and motivation. A theoretical framework provides researchers a structure and guide that can be used to help explain the process needed to achieve the goal of a project. The Health Belief Model was used to guide this project (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. Extended Health Belief Model

Health Belief Model

According to Sharma and Romas (2012), the Health Belief Model (HBM) is one of the theories created solely for “health-related behavior.” It is called a “model” but it has all the criteria of a theory (Sharma & Romas, 2012). The HBM was created in 1950 by U.S. social psychologists Hochbaum, Kegels, and Rosentock while working in Public Health (Sharma & Romas, 2012). The HBM was created out of the effort to understand why the free screening for tuberculosis was not effective (Sharma & Romas, 2012). The researchers found that the patients were not taking advantage of the free screening due to patient factors associated with limited knowledge, and perceived susceptibility to contracting the disease.

The HBM is frequently used in nursing when investigating patients’ compliance with treatment and disease prevention (Polit & Beck, 2012). This model proposes that a person’s health-seeking action is affected by his awareness of a threat that is imposed by his current health condition. The model postulates that taking action is necessary to decrease an impending risk associated with the threat of illness (Polit & Beck, 2012). In this model, the more a person realizes the danger of his/her current health practices towards his/her body, the more that he/she will be willing to change his/her behavior for better health.

The constructs of HBM are congruent with the features of a middle-range theory (Adams, Hall, & Fulghum, 2014). Nurse researchers use middle-range theories because these theories focus on phenomena such as health-promoting behaviors and use very few variables (Polit & Beck, 2012). The HBM has features of middle range theories, in that it is understandable, straightforward, comprised of only a few variables, and targets a

person's purpose of achieving a preferred health outcome (Adams et al., 2014). This model is comprised of six constructs. The constructs are perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefits, perceived barriers, cues to action, and self-efficacy (Sharma & Romas, 2012).

Health Belief Model Constructs

The first construct is *perceived susceptibility*. Perceived susceptibility is the person's belief whether they will develop a disease as a result of a specific behavior. There are varying degrees of how people perceive their susceptibility. Some people may be in denial, while others believe that they can contract a disease but doubt that it will happen to them. Lastly, there are those who worry that they will contract the disease no matter what they do to prevent it. The more vulnerable people feel, the more likely that they will take preventative actions (Sharma & Romas, 2012).

The second construct is *perceived severity*. Perceived severity is the person's belief regarding the magnitude of harm resulting from the disease due to a specific behavior. Every person has different insights about his/her disease; one might view this from a medical standpoint as disease symptomatology. Others may view their disease as a natural progression that eventually leads to death. For others, it can have a negative effect towards work, family, and personal relationships. With perceived severity, the healthcare provider should explain the harmful effects of the disease as it affects the whole person and the other parts of his/her life not just an overview of the disease (Sharma & Romas, 2012).

The third construct is *perceived benefits*. Perceived benefit is a person's belief that there are benefits in changing a certain behavior to reduce disease severity (Sharma

& Romas, 2012). This benefit should outweigh the harm of the disease and incentivize the person to change his/her behavior in a positive way.

The fourth construct is *perceived barriers*. Perceived barriers are the attitudes, and other factors that can be a hindrance to performing the behavior suggested or needed to achieve health promotion (Sharma & Romas, 2012). Barriers can be psychosocial, economic, and/or physical (Adams et al., 2014). These perceived barriers must be addressed to achieve the perceived benefits of the health-promoting behavior.

The fifth construct is *cues to action*. Cues to action are the things that motivate a person to change his/her behavior because of imminent threat of disease or illness. In the HBM, cues to action can be a telephone call or a pamphlet to help achieve health-promoting behavior (Sharma & Romas, 2012).

The last construct of the HBM is *self-efficacy*. Self-efficacy is the assurance in one's ability to take an action toward a health-promoting behavior. This construct was added to the model in the 1980's. Sharma and Romas (2012) suggested four approaches to enhanced self-efficacy. They are 1) divide complex behavior into small and attainable steps, 2) use a trustworthy role model for presentation, 3) persuade and reassure at all times, and 4) reduce stress.

Health Belief Model Literature Review

The HBM has been used successfully in a variety of research projects. Vadhariya and Sansgiry (2015) used the HBM in their study to assess knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors of people about the Ebola outbreak in Houston, Texas. They surveyed 283 people measuring: perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived threat, Ebola knowledge, self-efficacy, and health beliefs. The perceived threat, perceived

susceptibility, education level and those following the news were all found to be significant factors affecting a person's perception regarding their belief about the threat and susceptibility to Ebola. As a result of this study, it was determined that educating people about Ebola in the US through different methods can promote positive behaviors in the event of a future outbreak (Vadhariya & Sansgiry, 2015).

In another study, Dehghani-Tafti et al. (2015) used HBM to determine self-care predictors of diabetic patients. This was a cross-sectional study in Iran with 110 diabetic patients surveyed. The authors used all the HBM constructs as variables in addition to social support, self-care behaviors, and demographic information. According to their results, mean medication intake (6.48 times per week) was highest among those who engaged in self-care behaviors. In their results, perceived susceptibility and self-efficacy were predictive of positive diabetic self-care behaviors. However, perceived barriers had the opposite effect. The authors concluded that the HBM is a framework that is appropriate for developing and implementing diabetes health education (Dehghani-Tafti et al., 2015).

Application of HBM in Medication Adherence among Hispanic RA Patients

The HBM was the theoretical framework used to address the identification of barriers to medication adherence among Hispanic RA patients and developed an educational pamphlet (EP) to increase medication adherence. This framework was used to provide the foundation for the development of educational materials for diabetes. All constructs of the HBM were employed in this project (See Figure 2). The first and second constructs were the individual's perceptions of their disease. The perceived

susceptibility and severity of RA constructs were medication side effects, RA complications, pain, functional loss, disability, and death.

Modifying factors were comprised of demographics, perceived threat of RA, and cues to action. Demographics were the RA patient's age, ethnicity, gender, length of disease, socioeconomic status (SES), RA knowledge, beliefs, attitudes, and medication adherence. Perceived threats of RA were increased disease activity, increased pain, increased tender and swollen joints, joint destruction, and disease progression. Cues to action were the materials used to provide education, specifically the EP. The EP was developed after the identification of the perceived barriers targeting the educational needs of the patients.

Perceived benefits for patients were decreased pain or no pain, decreased disease activity, decreased or absent tender and swollen joints, no limiting or eliminating joint destruction, and/or achieving disease remission. Perceived barriers were cultural values/beliefs, health literacy, cost of medications, missed medication refills, preference for Spanish literature, methods of obtaining medication from pharmacy, SES, and educational level. Self-efficacy was a major component of this project. The patient must have confidence that they can achieve the goal of RA control, which results from medication adherence through the use of an EP addressing patient needs.

Figure 2. Modified HBM for Hispanic RA Patients.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A review of literature was conducted to gather the latest research applicable to the project. Electronic databases were searched for publications relevant to medication adherence. Databases used were the Cumulative Index to Nursing, Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), PubMed, Psych Info, and Google Scholar. These databases were accessed through California State University, Fullerton Pollack Library. Search terms used were “medication adherence,” “medication compliance,” “barriers to adherence,” “health beliefs,” “beliefs,” “attitudes,” “health literacy,” “self-efficacy,” “rheumatoid arthritis,” “patient knowledge,” “Hispanics,” and “Latino.” Limitations applied to the search parameters were peer-reviewed journals, adult participants only, English only articles, and articles published from 2005 to 2016. The RA treatment guidelines used for the project were released in 2015. The guidelines provided the rationale for the timeframe set in which articles were gathered.

Poor treatment adherence was a major contributor to disease progression, which can lead to disability. Among the Hispanic population, the adherence rates were 49% (White, 2014). There were factors, which facilitated or created barriers to treatment adherence. Patient’s knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes contributed to adherence. Practitioners can affect changes in a patient’s treatment, which can influence their knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes toward their disease leading to increased adherence.

Facilitators and Barriers to Treatment Adherence

There had been a number of studies, which evaluated the barriers and facilitators to treatment adherence. A study conducted by Compton, Haack, and Charles (2010) regarding medication use among Hispanics, found that 60 percent of the patients had

difficulties associated with not understanding prescription instructions, coordinating drop off and pick up of their prescription, and cost. The researchers asserted that medication compliance could be attributed to four components: “motivation,” “knowledge,” “skills,” and “access” (Compton et al., 2010, p. 368). In their findings, patient’s “motivation” to take their medication led to increased adherence to treatment. The patient’s knowledge about their condition also increased treatment adherence. Better knowledge led to a higher likelihood of better self-care skills and adherence to treatment. The components all intertwine to affect the patient’s ability to adhere to his/her treatment regimen leading to positive health outcomes.

Facilitators to Medication Adherence

Healthcare providers can help to improve medication adherence. Healthcare providers who were able to communicate with patients about disease process and medication adherence assisted to ensure that the patient understands medical instructions and medication side effects (Bailey et al., 2012). Level of acculturation was identified as a factor, which facilitated medication adherence (Compton et al., 2010). Highly acculturated patients were more comfortable in accessing the American healthcare system and navigating the prescription process (Villagran et al., 2011).

Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy was another factor that influenced medication adherence. Self-efficacy was the assurance in one’s ability to take an action toward a health-promoting behavior (Sharma & Romas, 2012). It has been shown that self-efficacy was among the greatest predictors of “health-promoting behavior” in patients with chronic illness (Maeda, Shen, Schwarz, Farrell, & Mallon, 2013, p. 94). Self-efficacy was associated

with medication adherence (Blamey, Jolly, Greenfield, & Jobanputra, 2009; Maeda et al., 2013; Mishali, Omer, & Heymann, 2011). Whereas, among Hispanic RA patients', low self-efficacy was linked to poor medication adherence (Elliot, 2013; Spruill et al., 2014). However, patients with high levels of self-efficacy reported less pain with decreased use of pain meds and coping skills; while patients with low self-efficacy it was reversed (Blamey et al., 2009). To increase self-efficacy, which in turn increases adherence among RA patients, it was suggested that patients be educated about symptoms and medication management during each visit. Providers should validate information that was provided to patients to ensure they understand the information. This will create change to positive health behaviors, which can lead to increased medication adherence (Blamey et al., 2009; Cameron et al., 2010; Maeda et al., 2012).

Barriers to Medication Adherence

Language barriers and educational level can affect the Hispanic patient's adherence to medication. According to Compton et al. (2010), 45% of Hispanic patients have a sixth grade or lower level of education. Thus, the educational level of information that was presented in printed materials or the level of language used by interpreters may not be at a level in which most Hispanic patients may understand (Bailey et al., 2012; White, 2014). It was important to consider the health literacy level of information presented to Hispanic patients since it influenced medication adherence and health outcomes (Caplan, Wolfe, Michaud, Quinzanos, & Hirsh, 2014; Joplin et al., 2015).

Another barrier to medication adherence faced by the Hispanic patient was the lack of access to the healthcare system (Ransford et al., 2010; Villagran et al., 2011). Some Hispanic patients were unable to access clinics for disease management because of

lack of health insurance or adequate health insurance or being undocumented in the United States (Hu, Amirehsani, Wallace, & Letvak, 2013; Melton et al., 2015; Ransford et al., 2010). Without insurance or adequate insurance, patients were not able to access medications or treatment, making it difficult to manage their chronic conditions. Because of their worries and distress about their undocumented status, they had limited contact with the health care system, which then decreased medication adherence (Melton et al., 2015; Ransford et al., 2010).

Patients who were taking large numbers of RA medications were less likely to adhere because of the complexity of the treatment regimen (Assawasuwannakit, Braund, & Duffull, 2015; Elliot, 2013; Henriques, et al., 2012; Polinski et al., 2014). Increased number of medications made patients 1.7 times less likely to adhere to their prescribed medications (Salt & Frazier, 2011). The complexity of medication regimens can cause patients to miss doses of their medicine. Complexity of regimens and high costs were associated with poor medication adherence (Brown & Bussell, 2011; Colby, Wang, Chhabra, & Perez-Escamilla, 2012; Elliot, 2013; Hu et al., 2013; Iuga & McGuire, 2014; Mishra, Gioia, Childress, Barnet, & Webster, 2011). For Hispanic patients, this may be due to lack of insurance coverage, low socioeconomic status, and no permanent employment. Those with Medicare coverage have limited prescription benefits adding to medication non-adherence (Colby et al., 2012; Elliot, 2013; Hu et al., 2103; Iuga & McGuire, 2014; Mishra et al., 2011). Patients who were of low socioeconomic status were more likely to ration their medications, skip dosages, and not take their medication to delay the expense of having to obtain another refill (Garcia-Gonzalez et al., 2008; Mackey et al., 2012).

Experiencing medication side effects was a barrier to medication adherence. Patients feared medication side effects, thus if patients experienced any untoward effects of their medication they may stop taking it (Elliot, 2013; Garcia-Gonzalez et al., 2008; Gatti, Jacobson, Gazmararian, Schmotzer, & Kripalani, 2009; Henriques, Costa, & Cabrita, 2012; Polinski et al., 2014). Patients obtained most of their information from their healthcare provider (Bailey et al., 2012). It is imperative that physicians explained medication benefits, risks and side effects to the patients (Berenbaum et al., 2014; Henriques et al., 2012; van den Bemt et al., 2009). Patients who believed that they have not received all necessary information from their healthcare provider were less likely to adhere to their medication regimens (Henriques et al., 2012; van den Bemt et al., 2009). Healthcare providers who took the time to explain the benefits and risks of medications, assessed for side effects during each visit and had a good rapport with their patients were more likely to see increased medication adherence (Elliot, 2013; Schuz et al., 2011; van den Bemt et al., 2009).

Patient Education to Medication Adherence

The RA patient needs to understand their disease, treatments, pain and symptoms management, and medication side effects. Patients need to understand how RA may influence their personal life, job, and affairs (Makelainen et al., 2009). Thus, having basic knowledge improves the patients' perception of disease progression and medication regimen (Makelainen et al., 2009). It has been shown that patient education was more beneficial to the newly diagnosed RA patients than patients with longer disease duration (Makelainen et al., 2009). Providing patient education increased medication adherence.

One-on-one provider to patient education has proven to be the best means of information dissemination (Homer et al., 2009; Makelainen et al., 2009).

Hispanic Patients and Medication Adherence

According to van den Bemt et al. (2009) newly diagnosed RA patients were more adherent to medication than patients who had longer disease duration. However, among Hispanic RA patients, those with shorter disease duration and increased pain had poorer medication adherence (Spruill et al., 2014). This was based upon their beliefs about the effectiveness of the medications to treat their disease. Thus, having decreased pain because of taking medications was believed to increase acceptance of one's illness (Zwikker et al., 2014). Most patients believed that they need their medications to maintain health (van den Bemt et al., 2009). However, the study by Spruill et al. (2014) showed that Hispanic patients increased concerns over the side effects of their medications was significantly linked to poor adherence. Although this was inconsistent with other findings, this still makes medication adherence a significant issue requiring intervention in the Hispanic population. To increase medication adherence among Hispanic RA patients, it was suggested that the level of patient knowledge regarding RA treatment and medication adherence be evaluated at every visit in order to assist in increasing patient's knowledge. Healthcare providers should be culturally competent about the population they serve. Patient education about their medications, and the provision of customized interventions need to be developed to target the specific learning needs of the Hispanic population (van den Bemt et al., 2012; Zwikker et al., 2013; Zwikker et al., 2014).

Interventions to Improve Adherence

There were different approaches used to improve medication adherence. These interventions involved the patient-healthcare provider relationship, behavioral interventions, patient education, and the healthcare system and financial interventions (Roberts, Wheeler, & Neiheisel, 2014). A trusting relationship between the patient and physician allowed for an open discussion about beliefs, culture, medication non-adherence, knowledge and concerns (Roberts et al., 2014).

Patient education, which included teaching and the use of printed materials should be part of building a trusting relationship. For patients with low literacy, educational materials should be printed in big print and at a third-grade reading level. And, if possible, the use of pictures allowed for better access to knowledge (Joplin et al., 2015; Mohan et al., 2012; Roberts et al., 2014). Among less educated Hispanic RA patients, the use of illustrations to provide medication instructions was effective in increasing medication adherence (Mohan et al., 2012). The patients were able to understand instructions provided through the use of pictures, symbols, numbers and simple instruction provided in Spanish.

Behavioral interventions targeting patients with physical limitations, mental impairments, and complicated treatment regimens helped to increase medication adherence. For these patients, pill boxes, easy open medication bottles, medication reminders, linking medication timing to a daily habit, and simplifying medication regimens also helped increased medication adherence (Roberts et al., 2014). Another behavioral intervention was the promotion of self-care management. When faced with spiritual and/or cultural barriers to medication adherence, it was suggested that physicians

use the “LEARN” framework to better comprehend the patient’s values. LEARN stands for: “L = listen with empathy, E = Explore and understand patient beliefs, A = Acknowledge differences between patient and provider beliefs, R = Recommend treatment, and N = Negotiate agreement” (Roberts et al., 2014, p. 285).

In conclusion, medication adherence among Hispanic RA patients was a problem. There were barriers that affected medication adherence such as patients’ beliefs, language barriers, immigration status, literacy, knowledge, and health care system access. However, once these barriers were assessed and addressed a solution to improve medication adherence was found. Little was known about improving medication adherence among Hispanic RA patients. However, the literature identified that, in general, with Hispanics, having trust and a good relationship with a provider were the key to successful treatment of RA. Patients’ knowledge about RA, information about medications and side effects, and providing educational materials that have low literacy, and that were culturally appropriate increased medication adherence. This project aimed to develop a theoretically driven, culturally sensitive and literacy appropriate EP to increase medication adherence among Hispanic RA patients.

METHODS

The methods section provides information regarding the design of the project; proposed research questions, operational definitions, and assumptions of the project. The independent, dependent, and extraneous variables were presented, followed by identification of the study setting and inclusion-exclusion criteria for the participant sample. A description of the instruments used in the project as well as procedures for data collection, procedures for protection of human participants, and statistical analysis procedures were also presented in this section.

Study Design

A pilot project using a quasi-experimental pretest – post-test design was used to develop and evaluate the effectiveness of a theoretically driven EP designed to increase medication adherence using strategies targeting Hispanic RA patients. To gather information about patients' knowledge, beliefs and medication adherence a self-administered pre-questionnaire was distributed to Hispanic RA patients at the participating clinic. This data was used as baseline information prior to the development and implementation of the educational pamphlet. The self-administered post-questionnaire was distributed after implementation of the educational pamphlet to determine if there was a change in knowledge, beliefs, and medication adherence.

Protection of Human Subjects

The Institutional Review Board (IRB) at the medical center in the clinic of study and at California State University, Los Angeles, was obtained. Participant information was kept confidential by adhering to the regulations of the Health Insurance Portability and Protection Act (HIPPA). All data was de-identified and was kept in a password

protected single user computer, with the participant identification key kept separated in a locked drawer in the office of the project investigator. All files containing electronic data were closed when the computer was unattended. Protected Personal Identifiable Information (PII) was removed from completed survey instruments. All documents and data sheets that contain PII were destroyed when no longer required for the study.

Settings

The project took place at a Rheumatoid Arthritis clinic in an underserved community in Los Angeles County in California. The clinic treats over 70 patients a week who have varying degrees of RA disease activity. The RA clinic is open two days per week on Mondays and Tuesdays.

Sample

The sample consisted of Hispanic patients who: (a) are over 18 years of age, (b) fulfill 2010 diagnostic criteria for RA diagnosis, and (c) are able and willing to sign informed consent. Exclusion criteria for this project were patients with (a) overlapping or mixed connective tissue disease or (b) existing illness or comorbidity interfering with full treatment potential such as chronic infections, malignancy, advanced or decompensated heart failure. The sample size for this project was 53 participants.

Procedures

All Hispanic RA patients were informed of the project and asked if they would like to participate. Consent was obtained to participate in the project. Participants were informed as to the reason for the project and what was required of them to participate. To avoid the perception of coercion, a research assistant distributed and collected the consents and questionnaires, since the Principal Investigator (PI) is a Nurse Practitioner

(NP) working within the project facility. Data were analyzed to determine which patients were non-adherent to their medication regimen by gathering information about their beliefs and knowledge regarding RA.

Based on the findings of the self-administered pre-questionnaire, an EP was designed and tailored to address specific barriers identified by the questionnaire. The EP included information regarding different types, need, and side effects of medications, and disease process, causes, and progression. To improve readability of the EP the literacy level was limited to a sixth-grade level while using many visuals. The Flesch-Kincaid Grade Readability Level through Microsoft Word was used to determine the literacy level of the EP.

The EP was given to the patients who consented to participate in the project. Participants were evaluated for medication adherence by continuously monitoring and tracking their use of medication throughout the project. Disease activity was documented through the CDAI and DAS28 scores.

The patients were followed for six months to determine if the EP helped to increase medication adherence and change knowledge and beliefs about RA. The EP were mailed to the patients and/or be given personally on their clinic visit. Within the first two weeks of the implementation of the EP, the study participants, were asked if they have read the EP by a follow-up phone call. Once the study participant confirmed this, the post survey was mailed in three weeks with self-administered post-questionnaire again to evaluate if there are differences between the pretest and post-test assessment regarding knowledge, and beliefs about RA as well as medication adherence. The questionnaire data were used to determine if medication adherence increased after

implementation of the EP. The post questionnaire data were compared to the pre-questionnaire data to determine the level of change, which may be the result of the EP.

Instruments

The self-administered questionnaire included three different scales designed to assess the understanding the patient's beliefs and attitudes toward their RA and medication. The first survey was the Patient Knowledge Questionnaire (PKQ) on Rheumatoid Arthritis. The questionnaire included a 16-item multiple choice questions, which assessed the patient's RA knowledge about their disease, symptoms, tests, medications, exercise, and protection of joints. The questionnaire has been used in several studies with high reliabilities of 0.80 or higher (Ndosi et al., 2015; Neto et al., 2009). The score range for the questionnaire was between 3 to 30 points with the median score of 16. The higher the score, the more knowledgeable the patient was about his/her disease. The type of questions that the scale included were:

Can you choose two true statements from the following list?

Rheumatoid Arthritis:

- a. Inherited from your parents
- b. Starts after a joint has been damaged
- c. Is caused by cold damp weather
- d. Cause is not known
- e. May be triggered by a bacteria or virus
- f. Don't know.

The questionnaire had a reported Kuder Richardson internal consistency of 0.72, and a test-retest reliability of 0.81 (Hill, Bird, Hopkins, Lawton, & Wright, 1999).

The second scale was the Beliefs about Medicines Questionnaire (BMQ), and it assessed the patient's beliefs about the necessity and concern about his/her medication. The questionnaire included 10-items using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The total scores can range from 5 to 25 points. A high score indicated strong beliefs about the need for medication to maintain disease control. The scale included questions such as *My health, at present, depends on my medications* and *Having to take medicines worries me*. This questionnaire has been used with RA patients (Neame & Hammond, 2005). The BMQ had a Cronbach's internal consistency alpha of 0.80 for the specific-necessity and 0.75 for specific-concerns and the test-retest reliability of 0.77 for specific-necessity and 0.76 for specific-concerns (Horne, Weinman, & Hankins, 1999). The BMQ has been translated into Spanish. The Spanish version was called Cuestionario de Creencias sobre la Medicacion- (BMQ-Spanish). This version was administered to patients who preferred to receive the questionnaire in Spanish. This questionnaire has been validated in patients with diabetes and hypertension (Belendez-Vasquez, Hernandez-Mijares, Horne, & Weinman, 2007). The internal consistency of this questionnaire was valid and reliable for assessing beliefs about medications (Belendez-Vasquez et al., 2007).

The third scale was called the Simplified Medication Adherence Questionnaire (SMAQ) which was modified from the Morisky Scale. The SMAQ contained three questions taken from the Morisky Scale to improve the reliability and increase adherence-specific measurements. The SMAQ was a brief self-report questionnaire designed to assess medication adherence and accuracy of medication intake such as number of missed doses in patients with chronic illness. The questionnaire included six questions

that evaluated different aspects of patient adherence with medication regimen. The SMAQ has been validated using patients infected with HIV. The scale had a Cronbach's alpha internal consistency score of 0.75 and inter-observer agreement of 88.2% (Knobel et al., 2002). The scale was also translated into Spanish. The Spanish SMAQ version was validated in renal transplant patients and has a Cramer's-V convergent validity of 0.516 ($p < .001$) and inter-observer agreement (kappa) of 0.821 ($p < .001$) (Suarez et al., 2011). The total scores can range from 0 to 8 points. The higher the score on the SMAQ the less adherent the patient was to their medication regimen (Knobel et al., 2002).

Project Question

The question that was addressed in this project was: What are the barriers to medication adherence among Hispanic RA patients? The barriers identified were used to develop a theoretically driven EP to help increase medication adherence.

Operational Definitions

1. Patient knowledge was operationalized using the Patient Knowledge Questionnaire in Rheumatoid Arthritis, which assessed patient knowledge about RA. Patients that received a score of less than 16 were identified as low knowledge. Patients that scored 17 or higher were identified as having high knowledge of RA.
2. Patient beliefs about medication were operationalized using the Beliefs about Medicines Questionnaire-Specific, which assessed beliefs about the necessity and concerns about RA medications. Patients that received a score of less than 20 were identified as having low beliefs. Patients that scored 21 or higher were identified as having strong beliefs.

3. Patient medication adherence was operationalized using the Simplified Medication Adherence Questionnaire, which assessed medication adherence and accuracy of medication intake. Patients that received a score of 4 and above will be considered non-adherent to medication.
4. Patient literacy level was operationalized by the patient's highest grade level completed. If the patient completed third grade, the patient would then be considered a third-grade level reader.

Assumptions

There were several assumptions in this project. One assumption pertained to the patients. It was assumed that the patients were honest and truthful in their responses to the questionnaire. It was assumed that all patients had read the EP before their six months follow-up. This was accomplished by providing the patients a reminder by telephone call once the EP was distributed and before answering the post-questionnaire survey as well as in anticipation of the six months follow-up. Patient literacy level was assessed using their self-reported educational level. It was assumed that the patient's highest level of education was aligned to their reading level.

Variables

The variables of interest were beliefs, knowledge, and medication adherence. Demographics provided the descriptor regarding the population and the influenced they had on the variables of interest. Beliefs, knowledge and medication adherence were measured using the questionnaires targeting the specific variables of interest. Demographics included age, RA disease duration, gender, tender joint count (TJC), swollen joint count (SJC), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), C-reactive protein

(CRP), race, and years of education. The independent variables were the items manipulated in the project, which in this project was the EP. The dependent variables were the items, which were measured, in this project were beliefs, knowledge and medication adherence.

Data Analysis

Each participant was assigned a code/ID number. This was on all survey instruments and was kept separate from the data identifying the patient. Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) 23 for Windows (SPSS Inc, Chicago, Illinois). Analysis included ANOVA, chi-square tests, correlations, frequency counts, and a regression analysis. A regression analysis was conducted to determine, which variables had the most influence on medication adherence. The data were summarized using tables, graphs and figures.

Summary

A pilot project used a quasi-experimental pretest – post-test design to evaluate medication adherence among Hispanic RA patients in a clinic setting. The project consisted of 53 participants who consented to participate. The project question included: What are the barriers to medication adherence among Hispanic RA patients? The barriers identified were used to develop a theoretically driven educational pamphlet to help increase medication adherence. The participants completed three surveys during pre- and post-test periods. The surveys assessed the participant's beliefs and attitudes toward their RA and medication, RA knowledge about their disease, symptoms, tests, medications, exercise, and protection of joints, and medication adherence with an accuracy of medication intake. The participants completed the pretest survey in

September 2016. The participants will be provided an EP after IRB modification approval is obtained from the hospital in which the project took place. The surveys will be mailed three weeks after distribution of EP to be returned by mail in a self-addressed prepaid stamped envelope once approved. A reminder call will be provided to participants who have not returned the survey within a week of the mailing. Three months after the EP is distributed, at the participant's clinic visit, disease activity will be documented through the CDAI and DAS-28 scores. These scores will be compared to the pre-test assessment taken at the participant's initial clinic visits.

RESULTS (PRE-TEST ONLY)

The sample participants consisted of 49 females and four males with a total of 53 participants. The mean age of the participants was 53. The average length of diagnosis was 12.5 years. The participants ranged from three months to 35 years of being diagnosed with RA. All participants were Hispanic with an educational level of zero to 17 years. The participants described the number of joints involved in their RA at the time of the project as zero to 40. The questionnaire was administered in either English or Spanish. There were four participants who chose to complete the English questionnaire and 49 completing it in Spanish (See Table 1).

Table 1.

Demographic Data of Study Participants (n = 53)

Variables	Total n (%)
<i>Demographic Characteristics</i>	
Age in Years	
30-39	6 (11)
40-49	14 (26)
50-59	12 (23)
60-69	21 (40)
70-79	0 (0)
Gender	
Female	47 (88.7)
Male	6 (11.3)
Education in Years	
0-6	21 (39.6)
7-9	15 (28.3)
10-12	9 (16.9)
>12	7 (13.2)
Race	
Hispanic	53 (100)
# of Patients & Years of RA Dx.	
0-5	12 (22.6)
6-10	13 (24.5)
11-15	8 (15)
16-20	11 (20.7)
20-25	6 (11.3)
>25	3 (5.6)

Table 1, *cont.*

Variables	Total n (%)
<i>Demographic Characteristics</i>	
TJC	
0	34 (77)
1-5	0 (0)
6-10	6 (14)
11-15	2 (5)
16-20	1 (2)
21-25	0 (0)
>26	1 (2)
SJC	
0	29 (55)
1-5	18 (34)
6-10	4 (7)
11-15	2 (4)
16-20	0 (0)
21-25	0 (0)
>26	0 (0)
Pre-Test Questionnaire Preference	
English	4 (7.5)
Spanish	49 (92.4)

The present project consisted of two components, a question and an EP. The question addressed: What are the barriers to medication adherence among Hispanic RA patients? The barriers identified were used to develop a theoretically driven EP that helped to increase medication adherence. The variables of medication concern and

perceived need were examined based upon the BMQ to determine which variable influenced medication adherence most significantly and created a barrier to adherence. Medication concern appeared to be a more impactful predictor of medication adherence when compared to perceived medication need. The participants were divided using the medication concern variable to divide the participant sample into two groups (i.e., high and low). To facilitate interpretation of this interaction effect, the association between levels of BMQ necessity was examined separately among participants who reported high BMQ concerns (>15) and low concerns (≤ 15). The median split of 15 allowed for adequately and comparable subgroups.

Figure 3. Correlation graph of BMQ concerns, necessity and SMAQ adherence.

A 2 X 2 factorial ANOVA was conducted to determine the influence of medication concern on adherence along with the interaction between medication concerns

and medication needs. The results demonstrated that medication concern and perceived needs were significant and marginally significant respectively. A significant main effect for BMQ concerns on medication adherence was observed, $F_{(1, 49)} = 19.75, p < .001$. The average adherence score with high concerns is 3.12 SD 1.34. The average level of adherence score with low concern is 4.38 SD 0.87. The main effect of BMQ necessity on adherence failed to reach criterion for statistical significance, $F_{(1, 49)} = 3.34, p = .074$. The average level of adherence score with high necessity is 3.90 SD 1.04 and the average level of nonadherence score for low necessity is 3.23 SD 1.57. There was also a significant interaction between levels of BMQ necessity and concerns, $F_{(1, 49)} = 4.78, p = .034$. To facilitate interpretation of this interaction effect, the association between levels of BMQ necessity was examined separately among participants who reported high BMQ concerns (>15) and low concerns (≤ 15). As shown in Figure 4, among participants with high BMQ concerns, those with high BMQ necessity reported significantly higher levels of medication adherence ($M = 3.63, SD = 1.01$) than participants low BMQ necessity ($M = 2.39, SD = 1.45$), $F_{(1, 30)} = 8.28, p = .007$. In contrast, among participants with low BMQ concerns, medication adherence was not significantly associated with BMQ necessity, $F_{(1, 19)} = 0.08, p = .779$.

Figure 4. Interaction effect graph of BMQ concern and BMQ necessity adherence.

Exploratory quantitative analysis of PKQ failed to yield significant findings. Descriptive analysis showed that most of the participants were scattered in their responses to the PKQ (Figure 5). Based upon the published guidelines scoring, only 3 (5.7%) participants demonstrated adequate knowledge about RA or had a PKQ score of 17 or higher which is indicative of high knowledge of RA. The majority of the participants scored 94% below the mean of 11.7 (Figure 6). This is a low level of knowledge. It is possible that the low PKQ scores that this attained by the participants in this sample limited the predictive potential of the PKQ as an independent variable. It is notable that there is a significant association between PKQ and level of education ($r = 0.543$ $p < 0.001$). Despite the lack of statistically significant findings, this is still clinically meaningful because it is apparent that patients were not comprehending and/or

understanding clinical information that were imparted to them during their clinic visits. The development and implementation of the EP is important in improving patients' knowledge about their disease and treatments.

Figure 5. PKQ pretest results distribution.

Figure 6. Histogram on PKQ Total scores of RA patients.

The disease activity measures were analyzed in comparison to patient demographics. The DAS28 CRP, which was a measure of disease activity based on blood work and tender/swollen joints, was significant when compared to age. The participants with low DAS28 CRP were more likely to be older participants ($r = -.354$; $p = .009$) see Figure 8. The CDAI was significant, which is a measure of disease activity with no blood components. The participants with low CDAI were more likely to be older ($r = -.308$; $p = .024$) see Figure 7. There were significant findings related to gender, which may not be meaningful for this project since the majority of the participants were female with only four males.

Figure 7. Line graph on correlation coefficient between CDAI scores and age.

Figure 8. Correlation coefficient line graph between Das 28 CRP scores and age.

DISCUSSION

The present project found that medication non-adherence was high among the participants. Participants with high medication concerns and high medication needs were found to have significantly higher level of medication adherence than those with low medication needs. However, participants with low medication concerns were not significantly associated with medication needs with their medication adherence. This indicates that with high need for medication, those with high concern were more likely to adhere to medication use. It appears that adherence to medication had multiple influences, with education being a contributor. Individuals with higher education were more likely to adhere to their medication regimen. The PKQ results showed that the majority of the participants had low knowledge regarding their RA.

The results from the pretest questionnaires are important in the development of the EP. Having very low RA knowledge specifically in disease symptomatology and medications, showed that RA patients need the EP to enhance their knowledge about their disease and treatment. The participants in this study had high percentage of medication non-adherence and perhaps did not understand the reasons for taking their medications. They lacked knowledge and concerned with taking their medications to prevent disease progression. With the results of the study, the EP will be developed to include RA symptomatology, treatments, side effects, and other information for a RA patient to understand their disease, management and potential prevention of disability.

The participants of this study had varying levels of education ranging from zero to 17 years. Their level of education had some effect on having very low knowledge. The study shows that patient education, which includes teaching and the use of printed materials should be

part of building a trusting relationship. For patients with lower literacy, educational materials should be written in big print and at a third-grade reading level (Joplin et al., 2015; Mohan et al., 2012; Roberts et al., 2014). If possible, the use of pictures will allow for better access to knowledge (Joplin et al., 2015; Mohan et al., 2012; Roberts et al., 2014). Among less educated Hispanic RA patients, the use of illustrations to provide medication instructions may be effective in increasing medication adherence (Mohan et al., 2012). The patients may be better able to understand instructions provided through the use of pictures, symbols, numbers and simple instruction provided in Spanish. The EP which is in development will be composed of pictures and simple instruction provided in both English and Spanish.

There were no significant findings related to the PKQ across all demographic variables except education. The PKQ was not predictive of medication adherence. Hence, a study by Joplin et al. (2015) found a number of factors contributing to non-adherence. Low educational level and limited health literacy were identified as the two major contributing factors for predicting medication non-adherence. Limited health literacy occurs when a patient does not understand the disease process nor the usefulness of taking these expensive medications to treat RA. Thus, having basic knowledge improves the patients' perception of disease progression and medication regimen (Makelainen et al., 2009). However, the implementation of an EP may assist with determining if the distribution of RA information will result in measurable findings upon post administration of the PKQ.

The participants in the study showed low concern with regards to their medication needs, which influenced their rate of adherence. The research showed that low medication concern would lead to low adherence. According to the literature reviewed for this project, most patients

believed that they need their medications to maintain health (van den Bemt et al., 2009).

However, the study by Spruill et al. (2014) showed that Hispanic patients increased concerns over the side effects of their medications was significantly linked to poor adherence. Although this is inconsistent with other findings, this still makes medication adherence a significant issue requiring intervention in the Hispanic population. In this project, low medication concern leads to non-adherence. This may be related to lack of knowledge regarding RA or the questionnaire may have been difficult for participants to interpret, given the low level of education of the participants. The participants had an average of eight mean years of education.

The HBM was used as the supporting framework for this project. Only data from the first phase of the project was obtained at this time. However, the use of the HBM framework allowed for barriers to medication adherence to be revealed. Medication adherence was under the second construct which was the modifying factors. It was found that beliefs about the medications such as medication concerns and necessity had a significant influence on medication adherence.

Future Steps

The project participants' knowledge of RA and medications were deemed very low. The participants had limited understanding of their disease and medication, which was evidenced in their low concern scores. Non-adherent participants may experience future negative consequences from not taking their medication which may increase disease progression and possible disability. If a patient takes his/her medications and suddenly develops side effects they are more likely to stop taking them. This is an indication of the limited knowledge of their RA treatments. With the development and implementation of the EP the participants may gain

knowledge about their disease, treatment, prevention of disease progression and thus adhere to their medication regime.

The EP will be distributed upon completion of the DNP program. This will fulfill the *cues to action* component of the HBM framework. The perceived benefits will be evaluated once participants complete the post-test assessment of the questionnaire. Baseline data, along with CDAI and DAS28 scores will be compared to the post-test scores and six-month clinic visit scores for CDAI and DAS28. The data will then be used to determine if the EP made a difference in increasing education to influence perceptions related to medication concerns and adherence.

Approval will be obtained from Harbor-UCLA IRB to distribute the EP. After distribution of the EP, the post-test questionnaire will be collected. The project will be completed in the summer of 2017; the clinical data may provide insight into changes in patient's behavior and knowledge regarding RA and medication after exposure to education. Blood work will show if adherence improved blood values which can be argued is the result of increased knowledge, and may be a mediating factor of medication adherence.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this DNP project showed that medication concerns and necessity significantly influenced participants' medication adherence. In part having low knowledge about RA possibly contributed to this factor. However, upon completion of the project the final results may show the benefits of the implementation of the EP to increase medication adherence.

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APPENDIX A

IRB APPROVAL LETTER

Compliance and Regulatory Affairs
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APPROVAL OF RESEARCH

September 19, 2016

Sally Moran
 smoran@labiomed.org

Dear Dr. Moran:

On 09/14/2016 the John F. Wolf, M.D. Human Subjects Committee (2) reviewed the following protocol:

Type of Review/Submission:	Expedited/Initial Review, Reference #041772
Project Title:	Medication Adherence Among Hispanic Rheumatoid Arthritis Patients
Investigator:	Sally Moran
LABioMed Project No.:	30980-01
Funding Agency:	LA BioMed
Documents reviewed:	Submission Response Form/Modifications Required to Secure Approval (Version 1.0) HRP-211: Submission Packet for Initial Review by IRB (Version 1.0) HRP-211: Application (Version 1.0) PHI Authorization (Version 1.2) Consent form – 9/14/2106 (Version 1.3) Investigator Protocol – 8/25/2016 (Version 1.3) Abbreviated Institutional Research Project Application (Version 1.0) Patient Knowledge Questionnaire in Rheumatoid Arthritis (Version 1.0) Spanish BELIEFS ABOUT MEDICINES QUESTIONNAIRE (Version 1.0) BELIEFS ABOUT MEDICINES QUESTIONNAIRE (Version 1.0) Spanish ADHERENCE QUESTIONNAIRE (SMAQ) (Version 1.0) ADHERENCE QUESTIONNAIRE (SMAQ) (Version 1.0) CV - George Karpouzas (Version 1.0) CV - Sally Moran (Version 1.0) Research Plan (Version 1.0)

The John F. Wolf, M.D. Human Subjects Committee (2) approved the protocol from 09/14/2016 to 09/13/2017 inclusive. Within 30 days prior to the protocol's scheduled Continuing Review (08/30/2017), you are to submit a completed "HRP-212: Continuing Review Progress Report" and required attachments to request continuing approval or "HRP-251: Final Report/Inactivation" to close the study.

Specific Condition of Approval:

- Human Subjects Bill of Rights – By California law a copy of the Human Subjects Bill of Rights, in a language in which the subject is fluent, must be given to all research subjects in this study as there is a real or foreseeable risk of biomedical harm. Numerous translations are available for download on the Compliance iRIS website at <https://imedris.labiomed.org>.
- All subjects must be able to consent for themselves to be enrolled in this study. This means that you cannot enroll incapable subjects who require enrollment by consent of a legally authorized representative.

Important Note: Approval by the IRB does not, in and of itself, constitute approval for the implementation of this research. Other LA BioMed clearance and approvals or other external agency or collaborating institutional approvals may be required before study activities and initiated. Research undertaken in conjunction with outside entities, such as drug or device companies, are typically contractual in nature and require an agreement between the institute and the entity.

If continuing review approval is not granted before the expiration date of 09/13/2017 approval of this research expires on that date.

Please see iRIS for the stamped approved consent documents and/or other study documents. Use copies of these documents to document consent.

In conducting this research you are required to follow the requirements listed in the INVESTIGATOR MANUAL (HRP-103).

Sincerely,

Signature applied by Elizabeth Burrola CIP on 09/19/2016 06:09:59 PM PDT

Liz Burrola, CIP
Compliance Office

cc: Elizabeth Hernandez
Office of Research Administration

APPENDIX B

QUESTIONNAIRES USED FOR SURVEY

PATIENT KNOWLEDGE QUESTIONNAIRE IN RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

SUBJECT ID# _____ DATE: _____

This questionnaire has been devised to help us find out how arthritis affects your life. All your answers will remain strictly confidential. Could you please answer the questions by circling the letter opposite your answer as in the example below:

1. What is the name of the type of arthritis you have?
- A. Ankyloing Spondylitis
 - B. Rheumatoid Arthritis
 - C. Fibrositis
 - D. Osteoarthritis

IT IS IMPORTANT TO TRY TO ANSWER ALL THE QUESTIONS

1. Can you choose TWO true statements from the following list?

- A. is inherited from your parents
- B. starts after a joint has been damaged
- C. is cause by cold damp weather
- D. the cause is not known
- E. may be triggered by bacteria or virus
- F. Don't know

2. Can you choose TWO true statements from the following list?

- A. affects only the bones of the body
- B. occasionally affects the lungs, eyes, or other tissues
- C. is most common in old age
- D. is a long term disease
- E. is curable
- F. Don't know

3. Can you choose THREE symptoms which can be caused by Rheumatoid Arthritis?

- A. Anemia
- B. Nodules
- C. Overweight
- D. Hair loss
- E. High blood pressure
- F. Fatigue
- G. Don't know

Page 1 of 5

PATIENT KNOWLEDGE QUESTIONNAIRE IN RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

SUBJECT ID# _____ DATE: _____

4. Can you choose TWO blood test which are used to assess how active your arthritis is?

- A. Cholesterol level (CL)
- B. Erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR)
- C. Blood group
- D. C- Reactive Protein (CRP)
- E. Plasma protein
- F. Don't know

5. Can you choose TWO true statements about non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs?

- A. They stop the disease from progressing
- B. They take may weeks to start working
- C. They reduce pain, swelling, and stiffness
- D. They need only be taken when the pain is bad
- E. They should be taken with food
- F. Don't know

6. Can you choose the ONE most common side effect that non-steroidal anti-inflammatory tablets can cause?

- A. Itching of the skin
- B. Indigestion
- C. Bruising
- D. dry mouth
- E. Loss of taste
- F. Don't know

7. Can you choose TWO "long-term drugs" which can put the disease into remission?

- A. Methotrexate also called Trexall or Rheumatrex
- B. Diclofenac also called Voltaren
- C. Leflunomide also called Arava
- D. Sulfasalazine also called Azulfidine
- E. Ibuprofen also called Motrin or Advil
- F. Don't know

PATIENT KNOWLEDGE QUESTIONNAIRE IN RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

SUBJECT ID# _____ DATE: _____

8. Can you choose TWO true statements about pain killing tablets?

Pain killers...

- A. are not addictive
- B. should only be taken when pain is severe
- C. should be taken before carrying out an activity which you know causes you pain
- D. should be taken when pain starts to build up
- E. should always be taken with food
- F. Don't know

9. Can you choose TWO correct answers about exercise and Rheumatoid Arthritis?

- A. It is unnecessary to exercise if you are normally active
- B. Exercise will cure rheumatoid arthritis
- C. Exercise weakens damaged joints
- D. Move your joints to the point of pain and then a bit further
- E. Exercise can reduce the chance of a joint deforming
- F. Don't know

10. Can you choose the TWO most suitable ways for someone with Rheumatoid Arthritis to take regular exercise?

- A. Muscle tightening exercises
- B. Gentle jogging
- C. Walking
- D. Yoga
- E. Shopping trips
- F. Don't know

11. Can you choose ONE activity which you should carry out when all your joints are painful and stiff?

- A. Refrain from all exercise
- B. Rest in bed for most of the day
- C. Carry out your usual range of movement exercises
- D. Exercise quite vigorously
- E. Don't know

PATIENT KNOWLEDGE QUESTIONNAIRE IN RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

SUBJECT ID# _____ DATE: _____

12. Can you Choose TWO treatments which would be most suitable if your wrists are becoming more than usually painful, swollen and stiff?

- A. Rest them by putting on wrist splints
- B. Reduce the stiffness by vigorous exercise
- C. Use them as much as possible
- D. Avoid movement by keeping them in one position as much as possible
- E. Put the joints through a full range of movement several times a day
- F. Don't know

13. Can you choose TWO sentences from this list?

The most practical way to protect your joints from strain is to

- A. use them quickly
- B. use the larger joints rather than the smaller ones where possible
- C. slide objects rather than lift them
- D. do as little as possible
- E. carry on as though you did not have arthritis
- F. Don't know

14. Can you choose the ONE most suitable activity when you have a busy day planned but realize you're feeling tired?

- A. Take the day off and do more tomorrow
- B. Do everything you had planned to do
- C. Take a short rest and then do all the things you had planned
- D. Do essentials and leave the rest
- E. Spend the day resting in bed
- F. Don't know

15. Can you choose TWO suitable methods of conserving your energy?

- A. Sit down while ironing
- B. Plan activities to balance work and rest periods
- C. Wear splints
- D. Use the strongest and largest muscles possible
- E. Use both hands to carry objects such as full saucepans
- F. Don't know

PATIENT KNOWLEDGE QUESTIONNAIRE IN RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

SUBJECT ID# _____ DATE: _____

16. Can you Choose TWO suitable methods of joint protection?

- A. Grip objects tightly
- B. Use a dish cloth rather than a sponge
- C. Use the palm of your hands not the fingers when opening a jar
- D. Apply heat or ice to the joint
- E. Having power assisted steering on your car
- F. Don't know

CUESTIONARIO DE LOS CONOCIMIENTOS DEL PACIENTE REFERENTES
A LA ARTRITIS REUMATOIDE

NÚMERO DE IDENTIFICACIÓN DEL PARTICIPANTE _____ FECHA: _____

Este cuestionario se ha diseñado con el fin de ayudarnos a averiguar cómo la artritis le afecta la vida. Todas sus respuestas se mantendrán en estricta reserva. Por favor conteste las preguntas marcando con un círculo la letra correspondiente a su respuesta como se indica en el ejemplo a continuación:

1. ¿Cuál es el nombre de la artritis que usted tiene?
- A. Espondilitis anquilosante
 - B. Artritis reumatoide
 - C. Fibrositis
 - D. Osteoartritis

ES IMPORTANTE QUE TRATE DE CONTESTAR TODAS LAS PREGUNTAS

1. ¿Podría escoger DOS afirmaciones verdaderas procedentes de la siguiente lista?

- A. se hereda de los padres
- B. comienza después de sufrir daño una articulación
- C. su causa es un clima húmedo y frío
- D. la causa se desconoce
- E. podría desencadenarse por bacterias o virus
- F. No sé

2. ¿Podría escoger DOS afirmaciones verdaderas de la siguiente lista?

- A. afecta únicamente los huesos del cuerpo
- B. de vez en cuando afecta los pulmones, ojos u otros tejidos
- C. es más común en la vejez
- D. es una enfermedad prolongada
- E. puede curarse
- F. No sé

3. ¿Podría escoger TRES síntomas que pueda ocasionar la artritis reumatoide?

- A. Anemia
- B. Nódulos
- C. Sobrepeso
- D. Pérdida de cabello
- E. Presión arterial alta
- F. Fatiga
- G. No sé

Página 1 de 5

CUESTIONARIO DE LOS CONOCIMIENTOS DEL PACIENTE REFERENTES
A LA ARTRITIS REUMATOIDE

NÚMERO DE IDENTIFICACIÓN DEL PARTICIPANTE _____ FECHA: _____

4. ¿Podría escoger DOS análisis de sangre que se utilizan para valorar el nivel de actividad de la artritis?

- A. Nivel de colesterol (CL, por sus siglas en inglés)
- B. Velocidad de sedimentación globular (ESR, por sus siglas en inglés)
- C. Grupo sanguíneo
- D. Proteína C-reactiva (CRP, por sus siglas en inglés)
- E. Proteína del plasma sanguíneo
- F. No sé

5. ¿Podría escoger DOS afirmaciones verdaderas referentes a fármacos antiinflamatorios no esteroideos?

- A. Impiden la evolución de la enfermedad
- B. Podrían tomar semanas en surtir efecto
- C. Alivian el dolor, la inflamación y rigidez
- D. Sólo es necesario tomarlos cuando el dolor es fuerte
- E. Deben tomarse con alimentos
- F. No sé

6. ¿Podría escoger EL efecto más común que pueden ocasionar las tabletas antiinflamatorias no esteroideos?

- A. Picazón de la piel
- B. Indigestión
- C. Moretones
- D. Sequedad de la boca
- E. Pérdida del sentido del gusto
- F. No sé

7. ¿Podría escoger DOS "medicamentos de uso prolongado" que pueden ocasionar remisión de la enfermedad?

- A. Metotrexato también llamado Trexall o Rheumatrex
- B. Diclofenaco también llamado Voltaren
- C. Leflunomida también llamado Arava
- D. Sulfasalazina también llamado Azulfidina
- E. Ibuprofeno también llamado Motrin o Advil
- F. No sé

CUESTIONARIO DE LOS CONOCIMIENTOS DEL PACIENTE REFERENTES
A LA ARTRITIS REUMATOIDE

NÚMERO DE IDENTIFICACIÓN DEL PARTICIPANTE _____ FECHA: _____

8. ¿Podría escoger DOS afirmaciones verdaderas referentes a tabletas analgésicas?

Los analgésicos...

- A. no ocasionan adicción
- B. sólo deberán tomarse cuando el dolor es fuerte
- C. deberán tomarse antes de practicar una actividad que se conozca ocasionar dolor
- D. deberán tomarse cuando comienza a empeorar el dolor
- E. siempre han de tomarse con alimentos
- F. No sé

9. ¿Podría escoger DOS respuestas correctas referentes al ejercicio y la artritis reumatoide?

- A. No es necesario hacer ejercicios si usted es una persona normalmente activa
- B. El ejercicio cura la artritis reumatoide
- C. El ejercicio debilita las articulaciones dañadas
- D. Mueva las articulaciones hasta sentir dolor y tras esto continúe un poco más
- E. El ejercicio puede disminuir la posibilidad de deformación articular
- F. No sé

10. ¿Podría escoger las DOS maneras más adecuadas para una persona con artritis reumatoide hacer ejercicios de forma regular?

- A. Ejercicios de contracción muscular
- B. Trotar de forma ligera
- C. Caminar
- D. Yoga
- E. Ir de compras
- F. No sé

11. ¿Podría escoger UNA actividad que deberá practicar cuando todas las articulaciones le duelan y se encuentren rígidas?

- A. No hacer ningún ejercicio
- B. Descansar en cama la mayor parte del día
- C. Practicar sus ejercicios habituales de rango de movimiento
- D. Hacer ejercicios vigorosos
- E. No sé

Página 3 de 5

CUESTIONARIO DE LOS CONOCIMIENTOS DEL PACIENTE REFERENTES
A LA ARTRITIS REUMATOIDE

NÚMERO DE IDENTIFICACIÓN DEL PARTICIPANTE _____ FECHA: _____

12. ¿Podría escoger DOS tratamientos apropiados si las muñecas desarrollaran más dolor, inflamación y rigidez de lo habitual?

- A. Descánselas usando cabestrillos para inmovilizar las muñecas
- B. Disminuya la rigidez haciendo ejercicios vigorosos
- C. Úselas lo mas posible
- D. Evite movimientos manteniéndolas en una sola posición siempre que fuera posible
- E. Someta las articulaciones a un rango completo de movimiento varias veces al día
- F. No sé

13. ¿Podría escoger DOS oraciones de esta lista?

La manera más práctica de proteger a las articulaciones de una distensión es

- A. usarlas rápidamente
- B. usarlas las articulaciones mayores en vez de las menores siempre que fuera posible
- C. deslizar objetos en vez de levantarlos
- D. hacer los menos posible
- E. continuar sus actividades como si no tuviera artritis
- F. No sé

14. ¿Podría escoger LA actividad más adecuada cuando tenga programado un día muy ocupado pero se da cuenta que se siente cansado?

- A. Tómese el día libre y haga más mañana
- B. Haga todo lo que tenía programado hacer
- C. Tómese un breve descanso y tras eso haga todo lo que tenía programado hacer
- D. Haga lo esencial y deje el resto
- E. Pásese el día descansando en cama
- F. No sé

15. ¿Podría escoger DOS métodos adecuados para conservar energía?

- A. Sentarse al planchar
- B. Programar actividades que permitan equilibrar el trabajo y los periodos de descanso
- C. Usar cabestrillos
- D. Usar los músculos más fuertes y grandes posibles
- E. Usar ambas manos al cargar objetos como las cacerolas llenas
- F. No sé

CUESTIONARIO DE LOS CONOCIMIENTOS DEL PACIENTE REFERENTES
A LA ARTRITIS REUMATOIDE

NÚMERO DE IDENTIFICACIÓN DEL PARTICIPANTE _____ FECHA: _____

16. ¿Podría escoger DOS métodos adecuados para proteger las articulaciones?

- A. Agarrar objetos firmemente
- B. Usar un paño de cocina en vez de una esponja
- C. Usar las palmas de las manos y no los dedos al abrir un frasco
- D. Aplicarle calor o hielo a la articulación
- E. Contar con dirección asistida en el auto
- F. No sé

BELIEFS ABOUT MEDICINES QUESTIONNAIRE

1

SUBJECT ID#: _____ DATE: _____

Please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with the statements below by marking with a circle in the number in the appropriate box.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Uncertain	Agree	Strongly agree
1-My health, at present, depends on my medicines	1	2	3	4	5
2- Having to take medicines worries me	1	2	3	4	5
3- My life would be impossible without my medicines	1	2	3	4	5
4- Without my medicines I would be very ill	1	2	3	4	5
5- I sometimes worry about long-term effects of my medicines	1	2	3	4	5
6- My medicines are a mystery to me	1	2	3	4	5
7-My health in the future will depends on my medicines	1	2	3	4	5
8- My medicines disrupt my life	1	2	3	4	5
9-I sometimes worry about becoming too dependent on my medicines	1	2	3	4	5

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BELIEFS ABOUT MEDICINES QUESTIONNAIRE

2

	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Uncertain	Agree	Strongly Disagree
10- My medicines protect me from becoming worse	1	2	3	4	5

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English Version

CUESTIONARIO DE CREENCIAS SOBRE LAS MEDICINAS

1

SUBJECT ID#: _____ DATE: _____

Por favor señale en que medida usted esta de acuerdo on en desacuerdo con las afirmaciones que aparecen a continuación marcando un circulo en el número de la casilla apropiada.

	Totalmente en desacuerdo	En desacuerdo	Ni de acuerdo ni en desacuerdo	De acuerdo	Totalmente de acuerdo
1-Actualmente mi salud depende de mis medicinas	1	2	3	4	5
2- Me preocupa tener que tomar medicinas	1	2	3	4	5
3- Mi vida seria imposible sin mis medicinas	1	2	3	4	5
4- Sin mis medicinas estaria muy enfermo/a	1	2	3	4	5
5- A veces me preocupo por los efectos a largo plazo de mis medicinas	1	2	3	4	5
6- Mis medicinas son un misterio para mi	1	2	3	4	5
7-En el future mi salud dependera de mis medicinas	1	2	3	4	5
8- Medicinas trastornan mi vida	1	2	3	4	5
9-A veces me preocupo por si llego a ser demasiado dependiente de mis medicinas	1	2	3	4	5

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Spanish Version

CUESTIONARIO DE CREENCIAS SOBRE LAS MEDICINAS

2

	Totalmente en desacuerdo	En desacuerdo	Ni de acuerdo ni en desacuerdo	De acuerdo	Totalmente de acuerdo
10- Mis medicinas impiden que mi enfermedad empeore	1	2	3	4	5

SUBJECT ID#: _____ DATE: _____

ADHERENCE QUESTIONNAIRE (SMAQ)

This survey is about medications you take for rheumatoid arthritis. For each of the following questions, please indicate which best describes your answer

1. Do you ever forget to take you medication? Yes No

2. Are you careless at times about taking your medication? Yes No

3. Sometimes if you feel worse, do you stop taking your medication?
 Yes No

4. Think back to last week. How often did you not take your medication?
 None 1-2 times 3-5 times 6-10 times More than
10 times

5. Did you fail to take any of your medication over the past weekend?
 Yes No

6. Over the past three months, on how many days did you not take any medication at all?
 No days 1 day 2 days More than 2 days

SUBJECT ID#: _____ DATE: _____

CUESTIONARIO SOBRE ADHERENCIA (SMAQ)

Esta encuesta se trata de medicamentos que toma para la artritis reumatoide. Para cada una de las siguientes preguntas, por favor indique que mejor describa su respuesta

-
1. ¿Alguna vez olvida tomar la medicación? Sí No
-
2. ¿Toma siempre la medicación a la hora indicada? Sí No
-
3. ¿Alguna vez deja de tomar la medicación si se siente mal? Sí No
-
4. En la última semana, ¿Cuántas veces usted no tomó la medicación?
- Ninguna 1-2 veces 3-5 veces 6-10 veces Más de 10 veces
-
5. ¿Usted se olvido de tomar cualquiera de la medicación en el último fin de semana? Sí No
-
6. En los últimos tres meses, ¿Cuántos días hizo usted no tome ningún medicamento?
- Ningún día 1 día 2 días Más de 2 días
-

APPENDIX C

TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Medication Adherence of Rheumatoid Arthritis Patients Table of Evidence

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Authors' Conclusions; Study Limitations & Your Notes
To evaluate med beliefs and self-efficacy of med adherence among H and AA with RA. (Spruill et al., 2014)	<p>Cross-sectional Study</p> <p>DV: Med Adherence</p> <p>IDVs: Demographics, DIS and treatment, Beliefs, Self-efficacy</p>	<p>$N = 56$ RA Pts H = 49 AA = 7</p> <p>USA</p>	<p>Med Adherence: MMAS = 8-item Likert Scale</p> <p>Demographics: Age (yrs): self-report Gender (M/F): chart review Race/Ethnicity (H/AA): chart review DIS duration (yrs): chart review Treatment (meds): self-report and chart review Comorbidities (htn, dm, hypcho): chart review</p> <p>Beliefs: BMQ = Two 5-item Likert scale Self-efficacy: MASSES = 13-item Likert Scale</p> <p>Cronbach's alpha scores not described.</p>	<p>Pts with shorter disease duration and increased pain have poor meds adherence ($P \leq 0.05$).</p> <p>↑meds concerns ($P = 0.04$) and ↓self-efficacy ($P = 0.007$) are significantly and independently linked to poor med adherence</p> <p>↑Beliefs in the need for RA meds was not related to adherence ($P = 0.68$).</p>	<p>Increase med concerns and low self-efficacy are linked to med adherence among RA H and AA pts.</p> <p>Author's Limitations: Cross-sectional with small convenience sample</p> <p>Lacking objective med adherence measurements</p> <p>Not generalizable within other minority group.</p>

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Authors' Conclusions; Study Limitations & Your Notes
Beliefs and factors that impact med adherence. (Neame & Hammond, 2005)	Cross-sectional survey DV: Med Adherence IDVs: Demographic Clinical Health Beliefs	<i>N</i> = 328 RA-DMARDs Pts UK	Med. Adherence: RAI = 5-item Likert scale Demographics: Age (yrs): self-report Gender (M/F): self-report Employment (current/retired): self-report Edu level (highest educational achieved): self-report Clinical: MDHAQ = 10-items Likert Scale and VAS -100 mm RAI = 5-item Likert scale AKQ RA specific subscale Form B = 11-item Likert Scale Beliefs: BMQ = Two 5-item Likert scale	F:220; M:108 Nonadherent for DMARDs were significantly more concerned about the need for meds than adherent Pt ($t = -3.136$; $P = 0.002$). 74% believed meds were necessary 47% were concerned with short term SE. 80% concerned about long term SE 56% concerned about dependency. Level of edu did not predict med adherence ($P = 0.66$). High levels of pain fatigue ($r = 0.24$; $P < .001$), and disability correlated with belief that meds were needed ($r = 0.36$; $P < 0.001$). After controlling for pain, fatigue and disability, the association between the necessity for meds and DMARDs taken persisted ($r = 0.17$; $P = 0.01$).	Med edu is not sufficient for adherence. ↑SE less likely to adhere. Med edu should focus on reassurance of safety of meds. Meaningful discussions about dx and meds with MD. Author's Limitations: Longitudinal study limited the causal relationship between concerns about meds and nonadherence. BMQ good screening tool for nonadherence. Note: This study uses the BMQ, a well-established survey.

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Authors' Conclusions; Study Limitations & Your Notes
			Cronbach's alpha scores not described.		
Account for confounders in RA outcomes related to med adherence. (Caplan et al., 2014)	Prospective observational study DV: RA med adherence HAQ IDVs: Demographics Health literacy	<i>N</i> = 6052 NDB participants USA	Med Adherence: MASRI = VAS 100 mm HAQ = 20-item Likert Scale Demographics: Age (yrs): self-report Sex (M/F): self-report Race/Ethnicity (white-nonhispanic): self-report Income (US\$): self-report edu (yrs): self-report comorbidities (0-9): self-report Health Literacy: SILS1 = One question Likert Scale SILS2 = One question Likert Scale Cronbach's alpha scores not reported.	79.6% of Pts indicated that their adherence to meds in the last mos as between 80% to 120%. Age, income, comorbidities and low health literacy had poorer adherence to meds. Low health literacy resulted in low med adherence (<i>P</i> <0.001).	Health literacy is an important factor in med adherence and health outcomes. Author's Limitations: Functional deficits could not be ruled out as a determining factor in health literacy or whether the functional deficit impacted med adherence. Population was limited to well educated, white-nonhispanic made study limited in generalizability.

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Authors' Conclusions; Study Limitations & Your Notes
To determine if their demographic factors affect the adherence rate to med as evaluate by pts. (Salt & Frazier, 2011)	Cross-sectional, descriptive predictive study DV: Med Adherence IDVs: Demographic Clinical	<i>N</i> = 108 RA pts. USA	Med Adherence: MARS-9RA= 9-item Likert Scale Cronbach's alpha = 0.77 Demographics: Age (yrs): self-report Gender (M/F): self-report Ethnicity (Caucasian, AA, O): self-report Edu (yrs): self-report Clinical: Disease duration (yrs) self-report # of meds (#) self-report	<i>N</i> = 98 adherent: Caucasian = 84 (86%) <i>N</i> = 10 nonadherent: Caucasian = 5 (56%) Caucasians pts 10 times more adherent to prescription meds (<i>P</i> = 0.012). Non-Caucasian pts 3-10 times more to report being nonadherent to prescription meds. ↑ # of meds makes pts 1.7 times more to not adhere to their prescribed meds (<i>P</i> = 0.02). No difference b/w the 2 groups in their demographic and clinical factors except ethnicity.	Ethnicity was the only significant predictor found in the nonadherence group. Non-caucasian pts are 3-10 times more nonadherent to their prescribed meds than Caucasian pts. Pts who take more meds are likely to be less adherent to their meds. Low level of educ and advanced age are not significant with med nonadherence. Author's Limitations: Sample consisted of mostly Caucasian F. Small sample size possibly didn't provide statistical power for other variables on med adherence Note: All Caucasian F sample and they are found to be adherent to treatment.

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Authors' Conclusions; Study Limitations & Your Notes
<p>To determine the influence of disease on adherence to meds among HIV+ & HTN pts. (Assawasuwannakit et al., 2014)</p>	<p>Meta-analysis DV: Med Adherence (pattern of dosages) IDVs: Different DIS (HIV, HTN), Age, REG, length of tx, type of med</p>	<p><i>N</i> = 404 articles Included 36 articles 24 HIV, 12 HTN USA</p>	<p>Med Adherence: MEMS devices Demographics: DIS: 0 = HTN & 1 = HIV; Age (yrs), REG; (1 to 3 etc); length of tx was the time in which the pt was taking their meds continuously; Type of med (med name) Pills daily (#)</p>	<p>Every 10 yrs a pts aged there was an 8% increase in med adherence. Increasing daily dosage there was a 4% reduction in adherence. HIV pts were less adherent than HTN pts. Every 10 yrs a pts aged there was an 8% increase in med adherence. $B_0 = .26$; Increasing daily dosage there was a 15% to 19% reduction in adherence. $B_3 = -1.10$ HIV pts were more adherent than HTN pts. $B_1 = 0.40$ There was a decline in adherence with decreasing age. $B_2 = 2.43$ Increase in dosage among older adults resulted in low adherence below 80%. $B_3 = -1.10$ Younger adults had overall poor adherence.</p>	<p>↑ in age cause improvement in med adherence. The more meds a pt takes the less adherent the pt becomes. HTN are more adherent than HIV pts. Aging and complex dosing predicts less adherence. Author's Limitations: Only two DIS were studies. Indirect measure of adherence using the MEMS. MEMS was a % of the # of pills taken. Missing data from studies extracted. The studies extracted had different goals then the purpose of the study. Note: The HTN would be equivalent to an RA pts in the sense that it is not an acquired dis such as HIV.</p>

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Authors' Conclusions; Study Limitations & Your Notes
To evaluate the use of group-based intervention to change med beliefs and increase med adherence among RA pts. (Zwicker et al., 2014)	<p>Randomized Clinical Trial</p> <p>DV: Med Adherence Med Beliefs</p> <p>IDVs: IG & CG IG: 2 MI guided sessions. The session involved improving pt concerns about meds and beliefs about meds. Cross sectional study and focus group. CG: received brochures about meds.</p>	<p>$N = 241$ IG = 123 CG = 118</p> <p>Netherlands</p>	<p>Med Adherence: MARS = 5-item Likert Scale</p> <p>CQR = 19-item Likert Scale Sensitivity of 62% & specificity of 95%.</p> <p>Demographics: Age (yrs): self-report Gender (M/F): self-report Edu level (bachelor's/master's degree): self-report employment (currently employed/studying): self-report DIS duration (yrs): chart review</p> <p>BMQ = Two 5-item Likert Scale</p> <p>All questionnaires had reported Cronbach's alpha = 0.68 to 0.95.</p>	<p>At 12 mos follow up there was a treatment effect. Beliefs about the need meds declined among the treatment than the CG. The IG reported ↓ pain and ↑ acceptance of illness. Adherence ↑ by 35% from baseline to 12 mos follow up; $P = 0.03$.</p> <p>Pts had ↑ need for med education.</p> <p>There was no difference between the two groups in BMQ.</p>	<p>The intervention did not change beliefs or adherence to meds.</p> <p>Author's Limitations: Intervention integrity was not good. DIS was more than 14 years for most of the pts. This will impact the ability to change beliefs. Both Internal and external validity was limited due to methods for measuring nonadherence.</p> <p>Note: There was a low attrition rate.</p>

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Authors' Conclusions; Study Limitations & Your Notes
To determine the nonadherence rate and identify risk factors to adherence among RA pts. (van den Bemt et al., 2009)	Descriptive Study DV: Med adherence IDVs: Demographic Clinical Psychological	N=228 RA Pts. Netherlands	Med Adherence: CQR = 19-item Likert scale Sensitivity 98% & specificity 67% Cronbach's alpha = 0.72 MARS = 5-item Likert Scale Cronbach's alpha = 0.78 Demographics: Age (yrs): self-report Gender (M/F): self-report Marital Status (married/living together): self-report Edu (Primary 0-6 yrs; Secondary 7-12 yrs; Higher >12yrs): self-report Smoking (smokers/nonsmokers): self-report Clinical: Drug (name and # of meds use): self-report DIS duration (yrs): self-report	Newly diagnosed RA pts more adherent to meds than pts who had longer disease duration ($P = 0.05$). Age, sex, marital status, edu level and smoking have no associations with meds adherence among RA pts. % of Meds Used: Methotrexate 56% Prednisolone 18% Hydroxychloroquine 10% Etanercept 8% Sulfasalazine 8% Adalimumab 5% % of Meds with SE: Corticosteroids 52% DMARD 39% Biologicals 27% Bisphosphonates 20% NSAID 16% Cardiovascular meds 11% CQR = 67% adherent total CQR = 20.3 adherent group and 19.1 nonadherent group ($t = 2.4$; $P = 0.02$) MARS = 60% adherent	No relation found regarding to demographic and clinical factors, information satisfaction, med concerns and coping styles with med nonadherence among RA pts. 2/3 adherent to DMARDs. This is lower when compared to the 98.5% who reported to their pharmacist that they were adherent. Most pts believed they needed their meds to maintain health. Meds adherence was related to disease duration, meds SEs and beliefs of meds necessity. Author's Limitations: Adherence overestimation because of Hawthorne effect. Adherence misclassification because of

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Authors' Conclusions; Study Limitations & Your Notes
			SEs: self-report Psychological: BMQ = Two 5-item = Likert scale Necessity Scale Cronbach's alpha = 0.81 Concern Scale Cronbach's alpha = 0.66		not having "gold standard" measuring adherence. Causal inference problems having used a cross-sectional design.
To identify predictors to med adherence among Latino pts. (Colby et al., 2011)	Cross-sectional study using retrospective data DV: Med Adherence IDVs: Demographic Socioeconomic Psychosocial	<i>N</i> = 61 DM Pts USA	Med Adherence: Morisky Scale = 4-item Likert Scale Cronbach's alpha scores not reported. Demographic: Age (yrs): self-report Gender (M/F): self-report Meds (#): self-report Socioeconomic: Economic (insurance coverage/ federal/state programs): chart review Psychosocial: MD support: self-report	↑ Number of meds associated with ↑ meds adherence (OR 1.24, 95% CI 1.04, 1.48, <i>P</i> = 0.016). 16 (26.3%) Adherent 45 (72.8%) Nonadherent ↑ Meds adherence among L associated with having support from MD. (OR 12.79, 95% CI 1.04, 157.21, <i>P</i> = 0.046). ↓ Meds adherence associated with receiving state and federal benefits (OR 0.06, 95% CI 0.01, 0.5, <i>P</i> = 0.010). L and AA, no insurance, ↑ copay less adherent (<i>P</i> < .001; <i>P</i> = .048)	Med adherence increased among Pts with controlled diabetes who had physician support. Pts receiving state and federal aide at more risk of non-adherence. Privately insurance pts less adherent when co-pays were elevated. Author's Limitations: med adherence was measured using one scale (Morisky Scale).

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Authors' Conclusions; Study Limitations & Your Notes
To evaluate associations of beliefs about meds and med non-adherence among RA pts. (Zwikker et al., 2014)	Cross-sectional Study DV: Med non adherence IDVs: Demographics Beliefs	<i>N</i> = 580 RA on DMARDS Netherlands	Med non-adherence: CQR = 19-item Likert scale MARS = 5-item Likert Scale Demographics: Age (yrs): self-report Gender (M/F): self-report living with others (y/n): self-report edu level (high/not high): self-report employment/studying (y/n): self-report Beliefs: BMQ = Two 5-item Likert scale All questionnaires had reported Cronbach's alpha scores of 0.68 to 0.97.	171 from 575 (29.7%) non-adherent per CQR 171 from 562 (33.6%) non-adherent per MARS. Indifferent attitude towards meds less adherent (Chi-square tests, <i>P</i> = .001). Limited influence of demographics & clinical factors associated with non-adherence. Med adherence and indifference toward meds was confounded by perceived benefits of RA	Increasing awareness about the need for meds will help to improve adherence. Belief in the need for meds was associated with adherence. No association regarding overuse and harm beliefs with adherence. Author's Limitations: Med non-adherence was ↑ in the study. Causality was not determined between beliefs and adherence. Note: Not able to determine which came first the belief and the nonadherence or the nonadherence and the belief.

Note: ADL's = Activities of Daily Living, AKQ = Arthritis Knowledge Questionnaire RA Specific, Pt /Pts= Patient/s, RA = Rheumatoid Arthritis, DMARD/S = Disease Modifying Anti-rheumatic Drug/s, BMQ = Beliefs and Medication Questionnaire, HAQ = Health Assessment Questionnaire, MASRI = Medication Adherence Self-Report Inventory, MDHAQ = Multidimensional Health Questionnaire, RAI = Rheumatology Attitude Index, VAS = Visual Analog Scale, SE/s = Side Effect/s, F = Female, M = Male, Dx = Diagnosis, MD = physician, Med/s = Medication/s, *N* = Sample, IDVs = Independent Variables, DV = Dependent Variable, ↑ = increase, ↓ = decrease, SD = Standard Deviation, *P* = p value, USA = United States of America, CQR = Compliance Questionnaire Rheumatology, MARS = Medication Adherence Report Scale, MMAS = Morisky Medication Adherence Scale, MASES = RA-adapted version of Medication Adherence Self-

Efficacy Scale, AA = African American, H = Hispanic, L = Latino, NDB = National Data Bank for Rheumatic Disease, SILS1 = Single-item Literacy Screening Questions 1, SILS2 = Single-item Literacy Screening Questions 2, edu = education, = = equal, # = Number, MARS-9RA = Medication Adherence Report Scale modified for RA, NSAID = Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug, RADAI = Rheumatoid Arthritis Disease Activity Index, y/n = yes/no, IG = Intervention Group, CG = Control Group, DIS = Disease, HTN = hypertension, DM = Diabetes, Hypcho = hypercholesterolemia, MEMS = Medication Event Monitoring System, O = Other, UK = United Kingdom, r = correlation, \$ = dollars, % = percent, HIV+ = Human Immunodeficiency Virus positive, REG = regimen, B_0 = intercept, B_1 = disease coefficient, B_2 = age coefficient, B_3 = dosing regimen coefficient, MI = Motivational Interview, mos = months, OR = odds ratio, CI = confidence interval, etc = an so f